

Presence at SOS 2016 for networking and visibility

Photo courtesy of WOC

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Blue-Action Deliverable D8.5

About this document

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Summary for publication

The World Ocean Council organised the Sustainable Ocean Summit 2016 (SOS) in Rotterdam, from November 30, 2016 - December 2, 2016. The SOS 2016 theme was “Ocean 2030: Sustainable Development Goals and the Ocean Business Community”. The SOS provides a global platform for leadership companies and organizations to advance the development and implementation of industry-driven solutions to ocean sustainability challenges. The inputs of the discussion at SOS 2016 will be taken into account by the Blue-Action WP6 and WP8, in particular when it comes to fostering an active exchange of information with business community operating in the Arctic and specifically to providing improved model data for significantly reducing operating risk in this region.

Work carried out

The 4th Sustainable Ocean Summit 2016 (SOS 2016) provides a global platform for leadership companies and organizations to advance the development and implementation of industry-driven solutions to ocean sustainability challenges. The SOS 2016 was held in November 30, 2016 - December 2, 2016 in Rotterdam, Netherlands and organised by World Ocean Council (WOC), partner in Blue-Action, an international business leadership alliance on Corporate Ocean Responsibility.

The SOS is designed to bring together leadership companies from the diverse Ocean Business Community: shipping, oil and gas, fisheries, aquaculture, seabed mining, tourism, renewable energy, ports, dredging, mining, submarine cables, marine science, engineering and technology, the maritime legal, financial and insurance communities, and others – as well as ocean stakeholders from the government, inter-governmental, academic and environment communities.

For more information on the SOS, such as the schedule, the online programme and the list of participants from various industries, please refer to the SOS2016 website: <http://oceanCouncil.org/resources-categories/woc-conference-and-workshop-reports/>

At the event, the Blue-Action project was represented by Nicole Biebow, coordinator of the H2020 project EU-Polarnet. The CSA EU-Polarnet and the other projects funded through the Blue Growth for supporting research and innovation activities in the Arctic, INTAROS and APPLICATE, are all clustered together with the Blue-Action project and constitute the Arctic Cluster 2016-2017.

Nicole Biebow led the SOS session “**Polar Region Sustainable Development: Business and Science Collaboration in the Arctic and Antarctic**”. This session saw the participation of actors interested in this specific regions and with the focus on connecting business and science. Nicole Biebow opened the session and shortly presented the Blue-Action project and the interest in connecting to the business community. A handout was provided to the participants.

Speakers in the session

- Nicole Biebow, EU-PolarNet (Chair)

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- Jeremy Wilkinson, British Antarctic Survey
- Annette Scheepstra, Rijksuniversiteit Groningen
- Juanjo Dañobeitia, Spanish National Research Council
- Sveinung Loset, Norwegian University of Science and Technology
- Lars-Henrik Larsen, Akvaplan-niva AS
- Eero Hokkanen, Arctia Ltd

Discussion

Nicole Biebow and Annette Scheepstra explained EU-PolarNet – the world’s largest consortium of expertise and infrastructure for polar research, comprised of 22 European multi-disciplinary research institutions. EU-PolarNet organized this session of the conference and hopes to achieve integration on polar research programs.

EU-PolarNet and the World Ocean Council share many goals, among which the improvement of dialogue and cooperation on Polar research. The World Ocean Council, who is partner both in EU-PolarNet and Blue-Action, develops programs such as *Smart Ocean-Smart Industry*, aiming at facilitating cooperation between the industry and the science community. The partnership between EU-PolarNet and the WOC on several projects has led to increase collaboration. As an example, a survey is conducted this winter 2016-2017 among the Polar business community to multiply cooperation opportunities for Polar data collection.

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Jeremy Wilkinson discussed projections of arctic sea ice loss. Climate change is affecting the arctic (and Antarctic) more quickly than the rest of the world – an average global temperature increase of 2°C in the world equates to a 6° or 7°C increase in the Arctic. Industry can help scientists model change by assisting with data collection in the arctic. As the ice recedes, shipping will be possible in the summer, but very difficult in the winter when there is near 24-hour darkness.

Lars-Henrik Larsen added that while there has been very little experience navigating long shipping routes in darkness to date, it will not be impossible.

Juanjo Dañobeitia explained the Polar Code – a mandatory international code for all ships (excluding fishing boats and fixed platforms) operating in polar waters. The Polar Code includes operational, safety and environmental measures, including anti-pollution procedures, fostering Polar sustainable development in the ocean business community. For example, the Polar Code declares polar waters “zero discharge zones” and explicitly prohibits any form of discharge or waste dumping. It came into effect in January 2017 for new vessels and will come into effect in 2018 for older vessels.

Sveinung Loset presented the Sustainable Arctic Marine and Coastal Technology (SAMCoT) initiative – a research coalition committed to capacity building in the arctic. SAMCoT represents a diverse group of stakeholders including 13 industry partners, 8 research partners and 2 public partners.

Ero Hokkanen expressed Arctia’s eagerness to collaborate with the global science community, reflecting the business community interest for cooperation. Arctia is a Finnish company that owns and operates icebreakers. Without icebreakers, Finland’s ports would be fully covered by ice in the wintertime and unable to conduct trade and shipping. Arctia hopes to collaborate with the science community to fill knowledge gaps and allow the collection of data on summer and winter arctic ice.

Q&A’s

Asked about opportunities for the private sector to invest in Polar research, panellists agreed that industry could work directly with scientists to evaluate risk that could affect their business. Some of this work is being carried out by governments, but there remain huge data gaps that will impact business.

Asked how to achieve better data sharing, Mr. Loset described the conflict for industry – they are very willing to be involved in data sharing as it will reduce risks for their industry, but they are also slowed down by economic competition. Ms. Biebow added that 60% of the arctic is owned by Russia and no research is allowed to be conducted there by foreigners. This lack of access has created a sizeable data gap.

Takeaways

- The Arctic is changing rapidly and industry collaboration is in high demand to fill data gaps.
- Collaborating with the science community will benefit the business community operating in the Arctic by improving models and greatly reducing operating risk.
- There are many opportunities for industry to engage in Arctic research, two of which were presented at this session: European research programs such as EU-PolarNet, and SAMCoT.

Text of the handout

Blue-Action is a four year H2020 project on **Arctic Impact on Weather and Climate** starting now and seeking to connect to the business community at the SOS 2016.

Blue-Action contributes to the implementation of the Trans-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance and to the EU's Blue Growth Agenda and its long term strategy to **support sustainable growth in the marine and maritime sectors** as a whole.

The project includes 40 partners from science **and industry** including **World Ocean Council, Det Norske Veritas, and Climate-KIC** (pronounced "kick") and is coordinated from the **Danish Meteorological Institute** in Copenhagen (by Steffen Malskaer Olsen).

The overarching objective of Blue-Action is to

- actively improve the ability to describe, model, and **predict Arctic climate change and its impact on Northern Hemisphere climate, weather and their extremes**, and
- deliver valuated climate services to business players and the society at large.

*Blue-Action has the specific objective to **foster the capacity of key stakeholders to adapt and respond to climate change and boosting economic growth** and to transfer knowledge to a wide range of interested key stakeholders.*

*Blue-Action has specifically targeted the **maritime sector** and is working directly with a number of stakeholders. Common to these activities is the focus on **planning, performance, and monitoring and risk assessment**.*

Specific services include:

- To develop forecasts for the distribution and timing of commercially important **fish stocks** in the Atlantic and Arctic sector
- To predict of **cold air outbreaks and polar low environments** and to incorporate this knowledge into **shipping** risk assessment tools.
- To quantify impacts of **resource extraction /mining** on Russian Arctic and to develop scenarios outlining possible impacts of climate change.

Climate changes in the Arctic are not just a risk for business in the Northern Hemisphere we need to tackle, we can help you turn it into a business opportunity !

How to connect to us?

www.blueaction.eu

Twitter @BG10Blueaction

Coordinator: Dr. Steffen M. Olsen at the Danish Meteorological Institute smo@dmi.dk

Main results achieved

The SOS 2016 has been a good chance to get introduced to the business community and to check the interest of further business stakeholders to be involved in or benefit from the activities of WP8 and WP6.

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The contacts of the speakers of the session might be of potential interest for some of the activities planned in the WP5, for instance in the case study on the polar lows.

The inputs of the discussion at SOS will be taken into account by WP6 and WP8, in particular when it comes to fostering an active exchange of information with business community operating in the Arctic and specifically to providing improved model data and to reducing operating risk.

The coordination of Blue-Action is closely collaborating with the FP7 ICE-ARC project (2014-17 www.ice-arc.eu) who is led by Jeremy Wilkinson at BAS. ICE-ARC is one of the projects clustering with Blue-Action in WP6. Flow of information and data within the cluster in WP6 will be ensured.

The cooperation with EU-Polarnet has been reinforced during the kickoff of the Blue-Action in January 2017: Nicole Biebow met the Blue-Action community and provided some interesting inputs for regular exchanges with WP6 and WP8. A Blue-Action representative will join the General Assembly of EU-Polarnet in early 2017.

Progress beyond the state of the art

Not applicable.

Impact

How has this work contributed to the expected impacts of Blue-Action?

The participation in the SOS 2016 was meant to inform potential stakeholders about the existence of the project and its goals. Ideally, the network of this project can be reinforced by the participation to SOS events in the future for:

- Improve the capacity to respond to the impact of climatic change on the environment and human activities in the Arctic, both in the short and longer term.
- Contribute to a robust and reliable forecasting framework that can help meteorological and climate services to deliver better predictions, including at sub-seasonal and seasonal time scales.
- Improve stakeholders' capacity to adapt to climate change.
- Contribute to better servicing the economic sectors that rely on improved forecasting capacity (e.g. shipping, mining).
- Improve the professional skills and competences for those working and being trained to work within this subject area.
- Improving innovation capacity and the integration of new knowledge.
- Strengthening the competitiveness and growth of companies by developing innovations meeting the needs of European and global markets; and, where relevant, by delivering such innovations to the markets.

Thus positively impacting the business sector in several ways.

Lessons learned and Links built

Unfortunately, the very first days of the project coincided with the date of the SOS 2016, and it was not possible for the coordination to join the SOS 2016 edition, due to the focus on the organisation of the Blue-Action kickoff meeting.

The participation to a SOS 2017 in Halifax, 29 Nov - 1 Dec 2017 is already in plan and take advantage of joint forces with the other projects in the WP6 cluster. The WP8 leader is planning to join SOS 2017.

A participation to future editions of SOS will also be scheduled to present the WP5 results.

Contribution to the top level objectives of Blue-Action

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives and specific goals indicated in the Description of the Action, part B, Section 1.1:

- **Objective 7 Fostering the capacity of key stakeholders to adapt and respond to climate change and boosting their economic growth**
- **Objective 8 Transferring knowledge to a wide range of interested key stakeholders**

The format of the SOS event is ideal for

- 1) collecting feedback from the business community and
- 2) to provide feedback to the business community.

References (Bibliography)

Not applicable.

Dissemination and exploitation of Blue-Action results

Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination activity	Title	Date and Place	Estimated budget	Type of Audience	Estimated number of persons reached
Participation to a conference	Sustainable Ocean Summit 2016	30 November to 2 December 2016, Rotterdam (NL)	//	Scientific Community, Industry Policy makers Medias Investors	
Press release	http://oceanouncil.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/WOC-News-Release-2017-01-19-	19 January 2017	//	Scientific Community, Industry Policy makers Medias Investors	

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	WOC-Partners-in-Research-on-Impact-of-Arctic-Changes-FINAL.pdf				
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Uptake by the targeted audiences

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is the general public (PU) and is made available to the world via [CORDIS](#).

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audiences:

This deliverable is available on the project website.

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Not applicable.